

**YO'L HARAKATI QATNASHCHILARI XAVFSIZLIGINING
HUQUQIY MANFAATLARI**

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son kasb hunar maktabi
yo'l harakati qoidalari fani o'qituvchisi**

Annotasiya: Maqolada yo'l harakati qatnashchilari xavfsizligini, ularning huquq va qonuniy manfaatlarini ta'minlash, yo'l-transport hodisalari sonini kamaytirish, mamlakatimizda haydovchilar tayyorlash va fuqarolarga haydovchilik guvohnomalarini berish tizimini tubdan isloh qilish, bu boradagi vakolatli davlat organlari mas'uliyatini yanada oshirish kabi masalalarga to'xtalangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yo'l, xarakat, qonun, jamiyat, ishtirokchi.

Аннотация: В статье предусмотрены обеспечение безопасности участников дорожного движения, их прав и законных интересов, снижение количества дорожно-транспортных происшествий, коренное реформирование системы подготовки водителей и выдачи водительских удостоверений гражданам в нашей стране, повышение ответственности компетентных государственных органов. в связи с этим были затронуты такие вопросы, как увеличение.

Ключевые слова: Путь, движение, закон, общество, участник.

Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi sohasida o'z yechimini kutayotgan ko'plab tizimli muammolar mavjud ekanligi sir emas. So'nggi yillarda yo'llarda harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlash va uning tashkiliy-huquqiy asoslarini tubdan takomillashtirish masalalari fuqarolarimizni, vakolatli davlat organlarini, keng jamoatchilik vakillarini, umuman olganda, jamiyatimizni o'ylantirib kelayotgan

asosiy muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Bu jabhada yo'l harakati qatnashchilari xavfsizligini, ularning huquq va qonuniy manfaatlarini ta'minlash, yo'l-transport hodisalari sonini kamaytirish, mamlakatimizda haydovchilar tayyorlash va fuqarolarga haydovchilik guvohnomalarini berish tizimini tubdan isloh qilish, bu boradagi vakolatli davlat organlari mas'uliyatini yanada oshirish, sohaga kirib kelayotgan yangiliklarning qonuniy asoslarini yaratish va huquqiy bo'shliqlarni bartaraf etish masalalari tezkor yechim kutayotgan muammolar sirasiga kirib ulgurdi. Ta'kidlash joizki, hozirda mamlakatimizda ushbu soha qator qonunchilik hujjatlari bilan tartibga solinganligiga va turli dasturlar, strategiyalar doirasida yanada takomillashtirish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan amaliy ishlarga qaramasdan yuqorida keltirib o'tilgan muammolar hamon saqlanib qolmoqda va alohida e'tiborni talab qiladi.

Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi sohasidagi munosabatlarni tartibga solishga xizmat qiluvchi normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar

Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi sohasi O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2013 yil 10 aprelda qabul qilingan "Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi to'g'risida"gi Qonuni hamda Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2015 yil 24 dekabrda 370-son Qarori bilan tasdiqlangan "Yo'l harakati qoidalarini" hamda ellikdan ortiq boshqa normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar bilan tartibga solib kelinmoqda. Masalan, "Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi to'g'risida"gi Qonunning 3-moddasida "yo'l harakati qatnashchisi – yo'l harakati jarayonida transport vositasining haydovchisi, yo'lovchisi yoki piyoda sifatida bevosita ishtirok etayotgan shaxs", "yo'l harakati xavfsizligi – yo'l harakati qatnashchilarining yo'l-transport hodisalari va ularning oqibatlaridan himoyalanganlik darajasini aks ettiruvchi yo'l harakati holati", "yo'l harakati xavfsizligini ta'minlash – yo'l-transport hodisalari yuzaga kelishi sabablarining oldini olishga, bunday hodisalar oqibatlarining og'irligini kamaytirishga qaratilgan faoliyat" tarzidagi huquqiy ta'riflar berilganligiga qaramasdan, huquqni qo'llash

amaliyotida mazkur normalar to'liq ishlamayotganiga yildan-yilga soni ortib borayotgan yo'l-transport hodisalari orqali yaqqol guvoh bo'lib turibmiz.

SHuning uchun ham 2022–2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan YAngi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasidagi 16-maqсад doirasida “yo'l infratuzilmasini takomillashtirish va xavfsiz harakatlanish sharoitlarini yaratish orqali yo'llarda avariya va o'lim holatlarini qisqartirish, shu jumladan harakatni boshqarish tizimini to'liq raqamlashtirish va jamoatchilikning ushbu sohadagi ishlarda keng ishtirokini ta'minlash” bo'yicha vazifalar belgilanganligi bejiz emas.

SHuningdek, Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2018 yil 20 oktabrdagi 841-son Qarori bilan tasdiqlangan “2030 yilgacha bo'lgan davrda barqaror rivojlanish sohasidagi Milliy maqsad va vazifalar”ning 3-maqsadi 3.6-vazifasida “2025 yilgacha yo'l-transport hodisalari sonini, jumladan, piyodalar tomonidan yo'l harakati qoidalarining buzilishi natijasida yuzaga keladigan YTH holatlarini ikki baravar qisqartirish” vazifasi nazarda tutilgan.

Yo'l harakati sohasidagi tizimli muammolarning tashkiliy-huquqiy yechimini topish maqsadida Davlatimiz rahbari tomonidan quyidagi vazifalar belgilandi:

Yo'l-transport hodisalari va qo'pol qoidabuzarliklar sonini kamaytirish yo'nalishida:

-mamlakatimizda 2021 yilda 10 mingdan ziyod yo'l-transport hodisasi sodir etilib, ularda 9 mingdan ortiq inson jarohatlangani, eng achinarlisi, 2 ming 500 ga yaqin odam halok bo'lgani va ulardan 263 nafari bolalarni tashkil etishi fojia ekanligi alohida ta'kidlandi. Qo'pol qoidabuzarliklar va ularni takror sodir etish holatlari ko'paygani sababli Oliy Majlis Qonunchilik palatasi va mutasaddi idoralarga yo'l harakatiga oid qonun hujjatlarini qayta ko'rib chiqib, tubdan takomillashtirish vazifasi qo'yildi. Bunda Davlatimiz rahbari yo'l harakati qoidalari eskirganini ta'kidlab, ularni xalqaro standartlar asosida, mutaxassislar va haydovchilar fikrini o'rgangan holda yangilash bo'yicha topshiriq berdi;

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